

Science

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CALCIUM FLUORIDE NANO PARTICLES FOR DENTAL APPLICATIONS

Mohammad S. Al-Ajely ^{*1}, Kareema M. Ziadan ², Rafed. M. Al-Bader ³

^{*1} Department of Chemistry, College of Education, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq

² Department of Physics, College of Science, University of Basrah, Basrah, Iraq

³ College of Dentistry, University of Basrah, Basrah, Iraq

Abstract

The aim of the present study was to prepare a calcium fluoride (CaF₂NP) Nano particle which is used in dental composites as dental filling compo glass type. CaF₂ Nano powders were prepared using a Co-precipitation method using binary liquid. Crystal Structural characteristics and Elemental composition of (CaF₂NP) Nanoparticles were predicted by X-ray diffraction (XRD), which showed crystalline peaks of this material. Elemental composition was obtained from EDX analysis. Morphology and diameters of the Nano fibers were studied by scanning electron Microscope (SEM). The size of the particles was also measured from SEM images about 58 ± 21 nm.

Keywords: Nano; Preparation; Characterization; Calcium Fluoride.

Cite This Article: Mohammad S. Al-Ajely, Kareema M. Ziadan, and Rafed. M. Al-Bader. (2018). "PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CALCIUM FLUORIDE NANO PARTICLES FOR DENTAL APPLICATIONS." *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 6(1), 338-346. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1167559>.

1. Introduction

Due to the importance of Nanotechnology in improving the physical and mechanical properties of a dental restorative material it has received considerable attention of researchers in this field. Alkaline fluorides (CaF₂, LiF₂, and BaF₂) are dielectric in nature and are widely used in microelectronic and optoelectronic devices such as wide-gap insulating over layers, gate dielectrics, insulators and buffer layers semiconductor-on-insulator structure and more advanced three- dimensional devices [1]. CaF₂NPs have a technological importance because of their potential applications including advanced phosphor, photonic [2], display monitors, imaging, and light amplification [3]. The extremely high laser damage threshold of Calcium Fluoride has made Calcium fluoride (CaF₂) is an attractive material due to its excellent properties: low refractive index, corrosion-resistance, thermal stability, and significant hardness, also cost effective and chemically stable, with good optical properties, and a deficiency of absorbance of visible light. Furthermore Low concentration of F in oral fluids derived from labile F reservoirs formed by the

use of F dentifrices and rinses have been shown to have a profound effect on the progression of dental caries (1–3). However, the low calcium (Ca) concentration in the mouth provides a limited driving force for the CaF₂ formation, and only very small amounts of CaF₂-like deposits are formed after a conventional sodium fluoride (NaF) rinse [4]. It was found that the composite containing 20% CaF₂ had a cumulative F release of 2.34 mmol/L at 10 weeks [5]. Other Resercher found that the initial F release rate was 2 g/(h cm²), and the sustained release-rate at 10 weeks was 0.29 g/(h cm²) [6].

There are several methods to the synthesis of CaF₂NPs which successfully prepare Nano scale material with controllable size and shape such as sol–gel method [7-9], solvo thermal process [10-12], reverse micelle method [13, 14], different precipitation methods [15-20], liquid-phase synthesis method [21], and flame synthesis [22, 23]. Co-precipitation is simple an easier method to synthesize Nano CaF₂ and it was used successfully to prepare Nano composites. Hydrothermal method is also a novel method to synthesize Nano particles of better quality [6, 17, 24, and 25].

The aim of this study was to synthesize CaF₂ Nano particles which is more important in dentistry especially in recent years in which the efforts focused on its use in light cured filling and intern could be used as a labile F reservoir for developing potentially more effective F regimens and as an agent for use in the reduction of dentin permeability.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

The starting materials used in the experiments were CaCl₂ (≥99.0%) purchased from Merck, NH₄F (≥95.0%) purchased from PRS Panreac (Barcelona Espana), and Ethanol (≥99.0%) From Fluka chemical company.

2.2. Preparation of Nano-Caf₂ Powders

(CaF₂NPs) Nanoparticles were prepared by co-precipitation method. CaCl₂ (0.01 mol) was dissolved in 100 ml distal water taken in 250 ml conical flask. NH₄F (0.02 mol) was added into the flask under vigorous stirring on a magnetic stirrer.

The mixed solution was stirred for 4 h which is gradually transform the transparent reaction mixture into opaque white suspension. Then, centrifuged for 15 min at 5000 rpm and washed three times with ethanol, centrifugation to eliminate the residual chloride and the ammonium ions. Finally the solid product was extracted onto a ceramic dish and dried on a sand bath. The reactions of CaCl₂ and NH₄F solutions show in the following Eq:

2.3. Characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were performed on SIEMENS, D5000 (GERMANY) using Fe K α radiation. The 2 θ angular resolution was 0.02. The diffraction patterns were scanned slowly over the 2 θ range 10~70, at a rate of 2 $^\circ$ /min.

The crystallite size (D) of CaF₂NPs was determined by the Scherrer equation [26]

$$D = \frac{\beta \lambda}{\cos\theta} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where λ is the wavelength of the incident X-ray (0.193604 nm), β Scherrer constant between 0.9 -1 depending on the particle morphology, in this experiment the average value of $\beta = 0.94$ was used giving for spherical crystals with cubic symmetry, θ is the diffraction angle and W is the full width at half maximum (FWHM in radian). Assuming spherical crystal, the diameter of the sphere (L) can be estimated [27]:

$$\langle L \rangle = \frac{4}{3} D \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where D crystallite size.

If the consideration is restricted to cubic crystal, the lattice planes spacing can be expressed as follows [28].

$$d = \frac{a_0}{\sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + l^2}} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

a_0 : lattice constant, here h, k, l are the miller indexes of the set lattice planes under consideration, we can write the quadratic form

$$\sin^2 \theta = \frac{\lambda^2}{2a_0^2} ((nh)^2 + (nk)^2 + (nl)^2) \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Micromorphology of the obtained nanoparticles was observed by scanning electron microscopy (VEGA TESCAN – Czech)

The IR spectra were obtained by using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, FTIR-8300, Shimadzu Co., Kyoto, Japan,) Spectra were obtained in the mid infrared region (400-4000 cm-1) with a resolution of 4 cm-1, averaging scans 32cm-1 per minute.

Multipoint BET (Brunauer-Emmett-Teller surface analysis is a technique for measuring specific surface area of the powders and porosity) surface area analyses were done (CHEMBET 3000 QUANTACHROME) with ultra-high purity nitrogen as the adsorbate gas and liquid nitrogen as the cryogen. The samples were dried in air overnight at 110 $^\circ$ C before the measurement. The particle size of the primary crystals of glass was estimated from the BET surface area by calculating equivalent spherical diameter, or BET particle. The mean diameter obtained by applying the BET method, dBET is represented by [29, 30]

$$d_{\text{BET}} = \frac{6}{A_s \rho} \quad (6)$$

Where A_s is the specific surface area (m²/g) and ρ is the theoretical density of the phase (g/cm³), Density measurements were performed on each sintered specimen using the pycnometric method [31]

3. Results and Dissection

Figure (1) shows X-ray diffraction patterns of CaF₂NPs powder. All the XRD peaks are indexed in to CaF₂ cubic phase of the fluorite type structure with space group Fm3m. The XRD pattern was found to match exactly with those reported in the literature [32]. All characteristic diffraction peaks at 2θ 35.819° (111), 60.264° (220), 72.044° (311), which are in good agreement with the standard values for the bulk cubic CaF₂ (JCPDS 87-0791). The calculated d values (lattice plane spacing) for the crystal planes (111) and (220) were respectively 3.14785°Å and 1.92834°Å, shown in Table 1, which were close to the standard values: 3.153°Å for (111) and 1.93°Å for (220), respectively [25].

The XRD patterns confirm the cubic crystallinity of the synthesized Nano particles. Using the (h k l) values of (1 1 1), (2 2 0) and (3 1 1) of different peaks, the lattice constant (a) of the samples were calculated. The average value of lattice constant was found to be $a = 5.45682 \pm 0.000204 \text{ \AA}$ which is in good agreement with literature value $a = 5.46250 \text{ \AA}$ (JCPDS 87-0791). The XRD pattern presents broad peaks revealing the small crystallite size of the synthesized samples. The Nano particles size was calculated using technique which uses Scherer's formula equation 2. The crystal size of CaF₂NPs obtained in the range $27.915 \pm 3.99 \text{ nm}$. The results match well with literature [5, 16, 24] and in agreement with JCPDF files 35-0816 for CaF₂

CaF₂-nano- File:X643.RAW-type 2Th/Th locked- start: 10.000° - End: 90.000° - step: 0.020-
 step time: 1. S – Temp.: 25°C (Room)-time start: 2S- 2Theta: 10.000° - theta: 35.000°- Phi: 0.00°-
 Aux1: Operations: smoth 0.044 | Background 56.234, 1.000| Import.

Figure 1: X-ray diffraction of CaF₂NPs powder

Table 1: The particle size analyses of a CaF₂NPs

2 θ degree	Miller index (hkl)	d value (Å)	crystalline size D (nm)	dimeter <L> (nm)	lattice constant a ₀ (Å)
35.819	(111)	3.14785	25.459	33.946	0.545483
60.264	(220)	1.92834	26.571	35.428	0.545673
72.044	(311)	1.64516	25.497	33.996	0.54589

The morphology and diameters of the CaF₂NPs show in figure 2. SEM image. The size of the particles was also measured by using the NIH Image program and the mean size of particles was 58 ± 21 nm calculated from approximately 100 Nano particles. The SEM picture shows that CaF₂NPs have many voids and are fluffy and porous. The larger particles exhibited numerous spherical perturbances on the surface, suggesting that they were formed during the precipitation process through fusion of the smaller particles. This result is close to what were a study reached such as Nandiyanto el at [21], Nakhaei [19] and Shahtahmassebi el at. [20].

Figure 2: The morphology and diameters of CaF₂ NPs measured by SEM

FTIR absorption was measured in order to show that the Oxygen bonds exist in the samples. The IR Spectrum of Nano crystals synthesized by co-precipitation method is shown in Figure 3. A Strong IR absorption bands at 450 cm⁻¹ and 3452 cm⁻¹ receptively belonging to Ca – F, H – O.

FTIR spectrum was also used to check the purity of the synthesized powder. Figure 3 shows the FTIR spectrum of the synthesized CaF₂NPs. This spectrum showed two strong IR absorption bands at ~3400 and 1550 cm⁻¹. They are characteristic of H–O–H stretching and bending of the H–O group. This finding reveals the presence of water molecules within the crystal structure of the prepared sample [16].

Figure 3: FTIR of CaF₂ NPs

Figure 4 shows the EDX spectra of CaF₂NPs, For Elemental composition obtained from EDX analysis, confirming peaks corresponding to the calcium and fluoride. The ratio of element was shown in Table 2.

Figure 4: The EDX spectra of CaF₂NPs

Table 2: Elemental composition (mass %) of CaF₂ NPs

Sample	ratio	O	F	Ca
CaF ₂ NP	Weight%	2.69	61.62	35.69
	Atomic%	4.33	74.38	21.30

One of the benefits of the mode of analysis is that it enables the power density distribution by pycnometric methods, the density was found 3.041 ± 0.006 g/cm³ and the theoretical density is 3.18g/cm³. The particle size of the primary crystals of CaF₂NPs was estimated from the BET surface area by calculating equivalent spherical diameter, BET measurements of the CaF₂NPs

gave a specific surface area found 25.279 m²/g. This corresponded to a particle size of ~ 70 nm assuming a density of 3.18 g/cm³ and a spherical particle shape for the CaF₂NPs, from the fundamental equation 6. This results were similar to those obtained by Pandurangappa [16] and Xu [24] which are 35 and 56nm respectively. The Properties of CaF₂NPs were tabulated in Table 3.

So CaF₂NPs was prepared successfully by co-precipitation method; this suggests that the CaF₂NPs could be a good agent for use in the reduction of dentin permeability furthermore It was successfully used in compo glass filling which is light cured type and will be published in next paper.

Table 3: Properties of CaF₂NPs

<i>d</i> _{XRD}	27.91547nm
Density	3.041 g/cm ³
BET specific surface area,	25.279 m ² /g
<i>SEM</i> average particle size (<i>d</i> _{SEM})	58 nm
BET equivalent spherical particle size(<i>d</i> _{BET})	70 nm

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

In the present work the Nano particle of CaF₂NPs have been successfully produced and applied in compo glass filling (our unpublished work) using the co-precipitation method.

The XRD data of these nanoparticles shows high crystallinity with lattice constant, in which (a) equal $5.45682 \pm 0.000204 \text{ \AA}$. The Nano particles size of CaF₂NPs obtained from Scherer's formula was within the range of $27.915 \pm 3.99 \text{ nm}$, From SEM images it was found between 40.49 nm and 92.35 nm.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the Iraqi Ministry of Higher Education and Research for offering Rafid the scholarship to do this work which is part of his PhD Thesis.

References

- [1] R. Singh, s. Sinha, p. Chou, n. Hsu, f. Radpour, h. Ullal and a. Nelson, preparation of baf₂ films by metalorganic chemical vapor deposition. Journal of applied physics, 1989. 66(12): p. 6179-6181.
- [2] T. Hase, t. Kano, e. Nakazawa and h. Yamamoto, phosphor materials for cathode-ray tubes. Advances in electronics and electron physics, 1990. 79: p. 271-373.
- [3] A. Bensalah, m. Mortier, g. Patriarche, p. Gredin and d. Vivien, synthesis and optical characterizations of undoped and rare-earth-doped caf₂ nanoparticles. Journal of solid state chemistry, 2006. 179(8): p. 2636-2644.
- [4] E. Saxegaard and g. Rølla, kinetics of acquisition and loss of calcium fluoride by enamel in vivo. Caries research, 1989. 23(6): p. 406-411.

- [5] H.h. xu, j.l. moreau, l. Sun and l.c. chow, strength and fluoride release characteristics of a calcium fluoride based dental nanocomposite. *Biomaterials*, 2008. 29(32): p. 4261-4267.
- [6] M.d. weir, j.l. moreau, e.d. levine, h.e. strassler, l.c. chow and h.h. xu, nanocomposite containing CaF_2 nanoparticles: thermal cycling, wear and long-term water-aging. *Dental materials*, 2012. 28(6): p. 642-652.
- [7] S. Fujihara, y. Kadota and t. Kimura, role of organic additives in the sol-gel synthesis of porous CaF_2 anti-reflective coatings. *Journal of sol-gel science and technology*, 2002. 24(2): p. 147-154.
- [8] B.-c. Hong and k. Kawano, syntheses of CaF_2 : eu nanoparticles and the modified reducing tcr treatment to divalent eu ion. *Optical materials*, 2008. 30(6): p. 952-956.
- [9] L. Zhou, d. Chen, w. Luo, y. Wang, y. Yu and f. Liu, transparent glass ceramic containing Er^{3+} : CaF_2 nano-crystals prepared by sol-gel method. *Materials letters*, 2007. 61(18): p. 3988-3990.
- [10] X. Zhang, z. Quan, j. Yang, p. Yang, h. Lian and j. Lin, solvothermal synthesis of well-dispersed M^{2+} ($\text{M} = \text{Ca}, \text{Sr}, \text{Ba}$) nanocrystals and their optical properties. *Nanotechnology*, 2008. 19(7): p. 075603.
- [11] G. Kumar, c. Chen, j. Ballato and r. Riman, optical characterization of infrared emitting rare-earth-doped fluoride nanocrystals and their transparent nanocomposites. *Chemistry of materials*, 2007. 19(6): p. 1523- 1528.
- [12] l. Zhengyi synthesis and characterization of CaF_2 : yb, er (core)/ CaF_2 (shell) up-conversion nanoparticles msc thesis 2010 national university of singapore
- [13] P. Aubry, a. Bensalah, p. Gredin, g. Patriarche, d. Vivien and m. Mortier, synthesis and optical characterizations of yb-doped CaF_2 ceramics. *Optical materials*, 2009. 31(5): p. 750-753.
- [14] Z. Xia and p. Du, synthesis and upconversion luminescence properties of CaF_2 : yb $^{3+}$, Er^{3+} nanoparticles obtained from sba-15 template. *Journal of materials research*, 2010. 25(10): p. 2035.
- [15] X. Sun and y. Li, size-controllable luminescent single crystal CaF_2 nanocubes. *Chemical communications*, 2003(14): p. 1768-1769.
- [16] C. Pandurangappa, b. Lakshminarasappa and b. Nagabhushana, synthesis and characterization of CaF_2 nanocrystals. *Journal of alloys and compounds*, 2010. 489(2): p. 592-595.
- [17] M. Azami, s. Jalilifiroozinezhad, m. Mozafari and m. Rabiee, synthesis and solubility of calcium fluoride/hydroxy-fluorapatite nanocrystals for dental applications. *Ceramics international*, 2011. 37(6): p. 2007-2014.
- [18] M. Mortier, a. Bensalah, g. Dantelle, g. Patriarche and d. Vivien, rare-earth doped oxyfluoride glass-ceramics and fluoride ceramics: synthesis and optical properties. *Optical materials*, 2007. 29(10): p. 1263-1270.
- [19] O. Nakhaei, synthesis and characterization of CaF_2 nps with co- precipitation and hydrothermal method. *Journal of nanomedicine & nanotechnology*, 2011.
- [20] N. Shahtahmassebi, m. Rezaee roknabadi and a. Kompany, synthesis and characterization of CaF_2 nps with co-precipitation and hydrothermal method. *Journal of nanomedicine & nanotechnology*, 2011. 2.
- [21] A.b.d. nandiyanto, t. Ogi, a. Ohmura, e. Tanabe and k. Okuyama, liquid- phase synthesis of CaF_2 particles and their low refractive index characterization. *Kona*, 2011. 29(141): p. 2011.
- [22] W.y. teoh flame spray synthesis of catalyst nanoparticles for photocatalytic mineralisation of organics and fischer-tropsch synthesis phd thesis 2007 the university of new south wales
- [23] R.n. grass and w.j. stark, flame synthesis of calcium-, strontium-, barium fluoride nanoparticles and sodium chloride. *Chemical communications*, 2005(13): p. 1767-1769.
- [24] H. Xu, j. Moreau, l. Sun and l. Chow, novel CaF_2 nanocomposite with high strength and fluoride ion release. *Journal of dental research*, 2010. 89(7): p. 739-745.
- [25] L. Sun and L.C. chow, preparation and properties of nano-sized calcium fluoride for dental applications. *Dental materials*, 2008. 24(1): p. 111-116.

- [26] A. Patterson, the scherrer formula for x-ray particle size determination. Physical review, 1939. 56(10): p. 978.
- [27] M. Meier, crystallite size measurement using x-ray diffraction. Department of chemical engineering and materials science, university of california, davis september, 2004. 13.
- [28] C. Kittel and p. Mceuen, "introduction to solid state physics". Vol. 8. 1976: wiley New York.
- [29] T.a. ring, "fundamentals of ceramic powder processing and synthesis". 1996: academic press limited elsevier.
- [30] S. Jain processing of hydroxyapatite by biomimetic process bachelor in technology 2010 national institute of technology rourkela
- [31] V.m. oremusová j., density determination of liquids and solids: manual for laboratory practice. (In slovak).
- [32] B.-c. Hong and k. Kawano, luminescence studies of the rare earth ions- doped CaF_2 and MgF_2 films for wavelength conversion. Journal of alloys and compounds, 2006. 408: p. 838-841.

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: mohamadalajelee@ yahoo.com